

Research Article

The relationship between dark triad personality and bullying behavior on vocational high school students

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Abstract

Bullying is a verbal or nonverbal behavior perpetrated by one individual or group against another individual or group. The bullying phenomenon has been the focus of education for a long time. One of the factors that can induce bullying in the individual is personality. There are three dark personalities within humans known as the dark triad personality. This personality is made up of machiavellianism, narcissism, and psychopathy. This study aims to determine whether there is a relationship between each dimension of the dark triad personality and bullying behavior. The method used in the study is the quantitative method, with the subject of 77 vocational students (15-20 years) who are ranked in the bully. The sampling technique used in this research is purposive sampling. The data was analyzed using spearman's rho's correlation. Research shows that there is a relationship in two dimensions of the dark triad personality with bullying behavior. Narcissism has the most positive relationships with bullying behavior and is followed by a psychopathy who has a positive relationship with bullying behavior. Additionally, studies also show that machiavellianism has no positive correlations with bullying. In order to reduce bullying behavior in schools, this can be done by integrating character education into the school curriculum to teach values such as empathy, respect and responsibility.

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Introduction

The phenomenon of bullying has been a concern in education for a long time. Bullying is something that can occur in various spheres. One of them is the scope of education or school. Based on data from The Indonesian Child Protection Commission, it was found that from 2016 to 2020 there were 915 cases of bullying that occurred in the scope of education. In 2020 there were 88 cases related to bullying in the scope of education. In addition, according to the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA in UNICEF, 2021) in 2018 revealed that as many as 41% of 15-year-old students had experienced bullying at least several times a month. The national assessment conducted by the Ministry of Education, Culture Research and Technology found that 24.4% of students in Indonesia have the potential to experience bullying incidents in the scope of education (CNN Indonesia, 2023).

In the adolescent phase, a person is looking for his identity who wants to be able to join his group, by hanging out and interacting with other people in the surrounding environment (Wijayanti & Nusantoro, 2022). In their growth, humans as individuals begin to get to know a wider environment than the family, so that the socialization experienced

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by individuals begins to expand. This makes individual social skills increase. In this case, if the socialization of good values that are instilled are not absorbed by children, then their behavioral and psychosocial development can be hampered. As a result, adolescents begin to show pathological symptoms such as delinquency and other risky behaviors, one of which is bullying (Zakiyah et al, 2017). Bullying behavior is carried out by adolescents to gain popularity so that they can dominate social life in their environment (Astuti, 2008).

Vocational high school is one of the places where bullying occurs in the scope of education (Agoes & Lewoleba, 2023). Vocational high school is a vocational education institution that aims to prepare students to work in certain fields (Hasbullah, 2012). Vocational high school students are required to have knowledge and skills in preparation as a skilled, educated, and professional middle-level workforce (Tambaru, 2021). In contrast to senior high school students who do not have special demands to be able to immediately join the world of work (Tambaru, 2021). Based on previous assessments, it was found that at this vocational high school there are several groups of bullying students. This group of students often verbally bully other students who tend to be quiet. In addition to direct verbal bullying, this group also conducts bullying through the class whatsapp group. In the past year, there was one case of verbal bullying against a student who had cancer so that this student experienced stress and was taken to a mental hospital to deal with his stress. When compared to high school students, vocational students have a greater risk of developing behavior patterns that are harmful to their health and engaging in bullying behavior (Horváth et al., 2018).

Bullying in the psychological dictionary refers to verbal or nonverbal violent behavior perpetrated by one individual or group against another individual or group (Husamah, 2015). Bullying is a type of aggression that refers to physical and psychological abuse or violence perpetrated by a person or group against another person (Pineda et al., 2022). Bullying can be direct and indirect. Direct bullying is physical or verbal violence. Meanwhile, indirect bullying is social or relational bullying where the victim of the bullying behavior is ostracized or rumors are spread (Salmivalli et al., 2021). Bullying can also occur through social media, commonly known as cyber bullying. Cyber bullying can be described as acts of violence through the internet or other digital technologies, such as spreading or uploading highly offensive content or using other forms of social harassment (Willard, 2007).

The impacts caused by bullying behavior include depression, feeling anxious, feeling depressed, suicidal thoughts, self-harm, and feeling dissatisfied with family, friends, and life (Wolke & Lereya, 2015). Bullying can also cause a lack of motivation or self-esteem, mental health problems, and fear (Yosep et al., 2022). Bullying behavior has a long-term impact, namely difficulties in socializing, if left until adulthood, the impact will be very broad, even the victims will experience problems in social relationships and low well-being in adulthood (Wachs et al., 2018). The National Youth Violence Prevention Resource Center (NYVPRC) shows that the impact caused by bullying behavior affects all involved, including the perpetrator, victim, and bystanders. The impact for the perpetrator is to have a very high sense of confidence and want to dominate in everything, the impact for the victim is to always feel fear and anxiety which can affect concentration and self-confidence, the impact for individuals who see is the emergence of assumptions that bullying is normal behavior so that it can increase the emergence of bullying behavior in individuals who see (NYVPRC; Norvian, 2017).

Bullying behavior can occur due to various factors. Factors that can lead to bullying behavior include individual factors, family factors, peer factors, and school factors (Azizi Yahya et al; Raharjo, 2023). If these four factors are not conducive, it can increase the tendency of adolescents to vent their emotions in a negative way. One way to vent emotions is by bullying (Jan & Husain, 2015). Other factors that can trigger bullying are economic differences, religion, gender, tradition, and seniority culture (Polanin & Vera, 2013). According to Armitage (2021), factors that can cause bullying include gender differences, age differences, non-compliance with gender norms, physical appearance, limited physical and learning abilities, differences in race, nationality, skin color, religion, social status, migration status, school environment, educational achievement, peer and family support. The desire to increase popularity among peers can also increase the emergence of bullying behavior. This is usually done by intimidating others (Haraldstad et al., 2019).

Personality is a collection of biological traits in the form of drives, tendencies, feelings and instincts, and tendencies acquired through experience in individuals (Sarwono, 1991). Each individual has special and unique characteristics, individuals also have their own needs that must be met and are associated with problems that cannot be assimilated by other individuals (Karim, 2020). Therefore, each individual reveals different characteristics based on their respective personalities (Karim, 2020). Individuals become one of the factors of bullying behavior caused by individual personality traits (Azizi Yahya et al; Raharjo, 2023). Bullies believe that they are constantly threatened and in danger. Bullies use attacks as support and justification for their aggressive behavior (Azizi Yahya et al; Raharjo, 2023).

Feelings of resentment, envy, and the desire to dominate the victim with physical strength can also trigger bullying behavior (Sekol & Farrington, 2016). Feelings of envy, and the desire to dominate are in line with the characteristics of narcissism in the dark triad personality. Jones & Paulhus (2014) stated that one aspect of narcissism is the desire to be a leader in order to dominate others. The use of physical strength or violence is also in line with the characteristics of psychopathy in the dark triad personality. Individuals with high psychopathy use charm and manipulate others for personal gain, do not care about the person being manipulated, and tend to behave immorally, inappropriately, to violence (Hare, 1999).

According to Coloroso (2006), bullying individuals have traits that like to dominate, like to take advantage of others to get personal desires, find it difficult to see situations from other people's perspectives, only care about their own desires and pleasures, and thirst for attention. These characteristics are similar to those of the dark triad personality. Dark triad personality explains that every individual has a dark side. The dark triad consists of a combination of three traits, namely machiavellianism, narcissism, and psychopathy (Afidah, 2019). Machiavellianism describes manipulative tendencies, a cynical attitude towards other individuals, and a lack of morality (Christie & Geis, 1970). Narcissism reflects a sense of superiority, enjoying attention, prestige, status, and praise (Raskin & Hall, 1979; Paulhus & Williams, 2002). Whereas psychopathy is characterized by a high sense of impulsivity, selfishness, lack of empathy, enjoyment of challenging things (Hare, 1985; Paulhus & Williams, 2002). Paulhus and Williams (2002) revealed that the dark triad consisting of machiavellianism, narcissism, and psychopathy associated with increased aggression may contribute to bullying behavior. Among the three traits, psychopathy has the strongest relationship with bullying behavior, followed by machiavellianism, and finally narcissism (Baughman et al., 2012).

Research on the relationship between dark triad personality and the level of bullying behavior conducted by Sadeghi & Alizadehfard (2022) to 200 male students studying in Tehran in the 2018-2019 academic year showed that the personalities of machiavellianism and narcissism have a direct effect on bullying behavior. Similar research was conducted by Bochen et al (2020). This study aims to explore the relationship between dark triad, peer relationships, and cyber bullying in high school students. The results of this study indicate that dark triad in middle school students has a positive correlation with cyber bullying.

Dåderman & Ragnestål-Impola (2019) conducted a study that focused on bullying perpetrators in adulthood scoring high on the dark triad scale. This study aims to find out what characterizes the personality of bullying perpetrators in the workplace and to find out its relationship with the dark triad. The results of this study revealed that machiavellianism and psychopathy are associated with bullying behavior in individuals. In addition, the study also revealed that bullies are callous, manipulative, extroverted, and people with high machiavellianism are the main bullies.

Resett et al. (2022) conducted a study in four prisons in Argentina. This study aims to explore demographics, personality, mental health, and attitudes towards bullying. This study was conducted on 667 male prisoners, 48 female prisoners, and 3 transgender prisoners. The results showed that bullying was predicted by higher levels of dark triad personality. Another research was also conducted by Panatik et al (2022). The research conducted was to determine the effect of dark triad personality on cyber bullying behavior among students. This research was conducted on 400 Malaysian State University students who were selected based on the convenience sampling method. The results of this

study indicate that dark triad is significantly correlated with cyber bullying behavior. In addition, this study also shows that psychopathy and machiavellianism have a positive and significant effect on cyber bullying behavior.

Problem of study

This study aims to determine the relationship of each dimension of dark triad personality to bullying behavior in Vocational High School students. This research is expected to contribute information and can be a reference for further researchers in the field of Psychology related to dark triad personality and bullying in adolescents. And can provide knowledge for readers about how the relationship of dark triad personality to bullying behavior in Vocational High School students. In addition, it is hoped that this research can serve as a basis for consideration of actions that can be taken to deal with adolescents who have high levels of dark triad personality and high bullying behavior, either through counseling or other treatments.

Hypothesis 1: There is a relationship between machiavellianism and bullying behavior in Vocational High School students.

Hypothesis 2: There is a relationship between narcissism and bullying behavior in Vocational High School students.

Hypothesis 3: There is a relationship of psychopathy with bullying behavior in Vocational High School students.

Method

Research Model

This study uses correlational quantitative research methods. The quantitative research approach is measured research that produces numbers (Anggara & Abdillah, 2019). The analysis in this study uses numerical data processing with statistical methods to test hypotheses (Azwar, 2013). This study examines the relationship between variables, namely dark triad personality and bullying behavior. This research was conducted by distributing scales through a survey.

Participant

The population in this study were all students at Vocational High School, totaling 220 students. The sampling technique that will be used is purposive sampling technique, which is sampling with certain considerations (Azwar, 2010). The considerations taken to be the sample in this study are students who are included in the indications of bullying perpetrators. The subjects of this study were 77 students who were included in the indications of bullying perpetrators at Vocational High School obtained after giving the HBSC scale to measure the level of bullying behavior.

Data Collection Tools

The variables in this study are dark triad personality and bullying. Dark triad personality is an independent variable in this study which will be measured using the Short Dark Triad Personality (SD3) scale which has been adapted into Indonesian by Hasanati & Istiqomah (2018). This scale measures the three main components of dark triad personality, namely: machiavellianism, narcissism, and psychopathy. The scale consists of 16 items with a reliability score of 0.849. Machiavellianism reliability score = 0.778. Narcissism reliability score = 0.73. Psychopathy reliability score = 0.823. The assessment of this scale is carried out using a 5-point Likert scale with the following options: Strongly Disagree is rated 1, Disagree is rated 2, Undecided is rated 3, Agree is rated 4, and Strongly Agree is rated 5.

While bullying is the dependent variable in this study which will be measured using the Health Behavior in School-Aged Children (HBSC) scale compiled by Roberson and Renshaw (2018) and has been adapted into Indonesian. This scale identifies various bullying behaviors including teasing, social exclusion, physical aggression, spreading lies, harassment, and cyberbullying. This scale consists of 22 items which are divided into 11 items to measure bullying victims and 11 items to measure bullying perpetrators. Based on the purpose of this study, the researchers only used 11 items used to measure bullying perpetrators. The reliability score of the bullying perpetrator measuring instrument is 0.736. The way the items are scored ranges from 1 to 5, where the following answer options are provided: Never in the last few months (score 1), Once or twice (score 2), two or three times a month (score 3), Once a week (score 4), Several times a week (score 5).

Procedure and Data Analysis

The procedure in this study consists of three stages, namely the preparation stage, the implementation stage, and the data analysis stage. In the preparation stage, it begins with preparing a research proposal and exploring theoretical studies related to the dark triad personality and bullying variables. Furthermore, determining the scale that will be used in the study. In this study, the scale used is the Short Dark Triad Personality (SD3) (Hasanati & Istiqomah, 2018) and the Health Behavior in School-Aged Children (HBSC) adaptation scale (Roberson & Renshaw, 2018).

The implementation stage begins with distributing the Health Behavior in School-Aged Children (HBSC) scale to all Vocational High School students. After that, it was continued with the administration of the Short Dark Triad Personality (SD3) scale to subjects with student criteria who had indications of bullying. The administration of this scale is done directly.

At the analysis stage, researchers analyzed the data using spearman's rho correlation analysis test. After the analysis is carried out, it is concluded how the dark triad personality relationship is with bullying behavior.

Results

In table 1, it can be seen that of the 220 students who have been given the HBSC questionnaire to measure the level of bullying, 131 students have no indication of bullying perpetrators. 82 students have low indications of bullying perpetrators, 6 students have moderate indications of bullying perpetrators, and 1 student has a high indication of bullying perpetrators. The subjects to be used in this study are students with indications of bullying perpetrators. Of the 89 bullying perpetrators students, only 77 students were able to participate until the end of the study. Therefore, the final subjects in this study amounted to 77 bullying students.

Table 1. Bullying perpetrator screening

Categories	Frequency	Percentages
Indications of Bullying Perpetrators		
Very High Indications	0	0%
High Indications	1	0,5%
Moderate Indications	6	2,7%
Low Indications	82	37,3%
No Indication	131	59,5%
N	220	100%

Table 2. Description of Research Subjects

Categories	Frequency	Percentages
Gender		
Male	73	94,8%
Female	4	5,2%
Age		
15 years	4	5,2%
16 years	40	51,9%
17 years	21	27,3%
18 years	6	7,8%
19 years	5	6,5%
20 years	1	1,3%
N	77	100%

Based on table 2, it is known that the research subjects were 77 students, with 73 male students and 4 female students. The age that dominates the most is 16 years old with 40 subjects.

Table 3. Dark triad personality scale data categorization

Categories	Frequency	Percentages
Machiavellianism		
High	44	57%
Low	33	43%
Narcissism		
High	34	44%
Low	43	56%
Psychopathy		
High	37	48%
Low	40	52%
N	77	100%

Based on table 3, data obtained from 77 subjects, 37 subjects were in the high dark triad personality category with a percentage of 48%. In the low category 40 subjects with a percentage of 52%. In machiavellianism, 44 subjects were in the high category with a percentage of 57%. In the low category there were 33 subjects with a percentage of 43%. In narcissism there are 34 subjects in the high category with a percentage of 44%. In the low category there were 43 subjects with a percentage of 56%. In psychopathy there are 37 subjects in the high category with a percentage of 48%. In the low category there were 40 subjects with a percentage of 52%.

Table 4. Normality test

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a		
	Statistic	df	Sig.
Bullying Behaviors	0,188	77	0,000
Machiavellianism	0,141	77	0,001
Narcissism	0,109	77	0,023
Psychopathy	0,111	77	0,021

Based on table 4, it can be concluded that the distribution of data on the variables of bullying behavior, machiavellianism, narcissism, and psychopathy is not normally distributed. This is because the significance level is less than 5% ($p < 0.05$) so that hypothesis testing is carried out using non-parametric analysis.

Table 5. Hypothesis test

Variable	Spearman's rho	Correlation Coefficient
Machiavellianism – Bullying Behavior	0,239	0,136
Narcissism – Bullying Behavior	0,017	0,272*
Psychopathy – Bullying Behavior	0,018	0,269*

n=77, *p < .05, two-tailed

Based on table 5, it can be seen that dark triad personality as a whole is related to bullying behavior in Vocational High School. The strongest relationship with bullying behavior from the dark triad personality dimension is narcissism, followed by psychopathy, and machiavellianism has no relationship with bullying behavior.

The first hypothesis in this study is that there is a positive relationship between machiavellianism and bullying behavior in students of Vocational High School. This hypothesis test was conducted using IBM SPSS Statistic software by testing spearman correlations with the results in table 5. The results in the table show that the correlation coefficient between the machiavellianism variable and bullying behavior is 0.136, then the coefficient of determination (r^2) is 0.018 which means that machiavellianism has a relationship with bullying behavior by 1.8%. Based on the table 5, it can be seen that the correlation of the two variables is not significant because the significance figure is 0.239 ($p > 0.05$). The

correlation is unidirectional, which means that there is no relationship between machiavellianism and bullying behavior in X Vocational High School students.

The second hypothesis in this study is that there is a positive relationship between narcissism and bullying behavior in students of Vocational High School. The results in the table 5 show the correlation coefficient between the narcissism variable and bullying behavior is 0.272**, then the coefficient of determination (r^2) is 0.073 which means that narcissism has a relationship with bullying behavior by 7.3%. Based on the table 5, it can be seen that the correlation of the two variables is significant because the significance figure is 0.017 ($p < 0.05$). The correlation is unidirectional, which means that there is a positive relationship between narcissism and bullying behavior in students of Vocational High School.

The third hypothesis in this study is that there is a positive relationship between psychopathy and bullying behavior in students of Vocational High School X. The results in the table show that the correlation coefficient between the psychopathy variable and bullying behavior is 0.269**, then the coefficient of determination (r^2) is 0.072 which means that psychopathy has a relationship with bullying behavior by 7.2%. Based on the table 5, it can be seen that the correlation of the two variables is significant because the significance figure is 0.018 ($p < 0.05$). The correlation is unidirectional which means that there is a positive relationship between psychopathy and bullying behavior in students of Vocational High School X.

Discussion

The results of the analysis show that narcissism and psychopathy have a significant relationship with bullying behavior. Only machiavellianism does not have a significant relationship with bullying behavior. When viewed from the coefficient of determination, it can be seen that dark triad personality is related to bullying behavior by 12.8%. Machiavellianism has a determinant coefficient value of 0.018, which means that machiavellianism has a relationship with bullying behavior by 1.8%. Narcissism has a determinant coefficient value of 0.073, which means that narcissism has a relationship with bullying behavior by 7.3%. Psychopathy has a determinant coefficient value of 0.072 which means psychopathy has a relationship with bullying behavior by 7.2%. The difference in the relationship shows that in the dark triad personality, narcissism has the highest relationship with bullying behavior and is followed by psychopathy, while machiavellianism has the lowest relationship with bullying behavior.

The results obtained in this study are supported by previous research conducted by Egorova & Adamovich (2018) on high school students in Russia which shows that there is a relationship between each dimension of dark triad traits and bullying behavior. Research conducted by Egorova & Adamovich (2018) used two instruments to measure dark triad personality, namely SD3 and Dark Triad Portrait Questionnaire. The results of the two instruments have differences, SD3 shows that psychopathy has the most relationship, followed by machiavellianism, and finally narcissism. While the results of the Dark Triad Portrait Questionnaire show that machiavellianism has the highest relationship with bullying behavior, followed by psychopathy, and narcissism has the lowest relationship with bullying behavior.

The results of this study are also supported by other research conducted by Adrianty et al. (2023) which aims to determine the effect of dark triad personality on bullying behavior in adolescents. Research by Adrianty et al. (2023) conducted on 100 adolescents with an age range of 13-18 years showed the results that there was an influence of each dimension of the dark triad personality on bullying behavior in adolescents. In addition, research conducted by Adrianty et al. (2023) also shows that psychopathy has the highest influence on bullying behavior, followed by machiavellianism, and narcissism which has the lowest influence. Similar research that supports the results of this study is research conducted by Asih & Lutfiyah (2023) to 292 individuals aged 20-35 years and aims to determine the role of self-esteem as a mediator in the relationship between dark triad personality and cyberbullying. The results of Asih & Lutfiyah's research (2023) show that the direct effect test results on psychopathy and cyberbullying traits have a significant

relationship. The results of the direct effect test on narcissism and cyberbullying have an insignificant relationship. The results of the direct effect test on the nature of machiavellianism and cyberbullying have an insignificant relationship.

Zhu & Jin (2021) revealed that each dimension of dark triad has a positive correlation with aggressive behavior. Bullying behavior is a form of violence and aggressive students at school (Trisnani & Wardani, 2016). Similar research conducted by Lim (2021) also revealed that the three traits in the dark triad personality predict juvenile delinquent behavior. Based on the results of data analysis in this study, it is known that two dimension of dark triad is positively related to bullying behavior. With these results, it explains that the second and third hypothesis is accepted, but not the first hypothesis.

The research data shows that machiavellianism and bullying behavior are not significantly related. Then the second hypothesis cannot be accepted. This finding is in line with the results of research conducted by Asih & Lutfiyah (2023) which shows that machiavellianism has no direct relationship with cyber bullying. However, these results differ from other research conducted by Dåderman & Ragnestål-Impola (2019) in Sweden which shows that machiavellianism has a positive effect on workplace bullying and machiavellianism can predict workplace bullying. This difference in results is due to cultural differences in the place of research. Smith et al (2002) showed that Indonesia has a strong tendency towards a culture of collectivism. In contrast to research conducted by Dåderman & Ragnestål-Impola (2019) in Sweden. Based on research conducted by Smith et al (2002) Sweden is a country that has a culture of individualism.

Some researchers state that individualism culture is associated with higher levels of aggression than collectivism (Widaningtyas & Sugito, 2022). Collectivism culture is a culture that upholds the value of group togetherness compared to personal interests (Luthans, 2006). Collectivism culture is more commonly found in eastern societies, including Asia (Durgel et al., 2012; Franke, Hofstede, & Bond 1991). Van Der Kroef (1953) said that Indonesians have a strong culture of collectivism because of the ancient pattern of *gotong royong*. The culture of collectivism can be seen in rural communities in Indonesia, including traditional Javanese communities (Geertz, 1992; Mulder, 1992; Mulder, 2000). The results of research conducted by Zahroh (2023) stated that the culture of individualism is a culture that is more concerned with individual interests than with group interests. Based on this, machiavellianism personality is not significantly related to bullying behavior because the culture in Indonesia tends to embrace a culture of collectivism, which is not in line with machiavellianism personality which is oriented towards one's own goals.

Bereczkei (2017) explains that there are five basic traits of individuals with machiavellianism. First, manipulation, trying to influence others and lying. Second amorality, which is willing to do anything without regard to existing norms. Third is cynicism, the tendency to look down on others. Fourth is emotionally cold, quiet and unconcerned about the surrounding environment. Fifth, lack of empathy, lack of understanding of how others feel. Machiavellianism is described as an individual who is cunning, selfish, lacks pro-social orientation, and is power-oriented (Rauthmann & Kolar, 2012). Therefore, Machiavellianism individuals are not interested in the actions of others in order to achieve their own goals (Tam & Ha, 2023).

The results of this study indicate that narcissism and bullying behavior are significantly related or positively correlated. This is in line with research conducted by Mutoharoh (2023) which shows that narcissism has a significant positive effect on aggressiveness. If the subject has a high narcissism score, then the likelihood of aggressiveness will also be high. Conversely, if the narcissism score is low, it is likely that the aggressiveness score will also be low. Reijntjes et al. (2016) in their research revealed that adolescent girls with high narcissism were not associated with bullying. In contrast, adolescent boys who have high narcissism have a greater likelihood of direct bullying.

Fanti & Frangou (2018) explained that individuals with narcissistic traits may be vulnerable to engaging in bullying behavior, as bullying involves deliberate actions designed to achieve social advantage and dominance over peers. Individuals with high levels of narcissism exhibit a strong sense of grandiosity, an excessive need for admiration, and an inability to show empathy (Morf & Rhodewalt in Fanti & Frangou, 2018). Bullying is considered a form of proactive aggression to dominate peers to reinforce grandiosity (Griffin & Gross in Fanti & Henrich, 2015). Adolescents with low

self-esteem and high narcissism are characteristic of bullying perpetrators (Fanti & Frangou, 2018). This is in line with the second hypothesis which is that there is a positive relationship between narcissism and bullying behavior. Then the third hypothesis is accepted.

The results of this study indicate that psychopathy and bullying behavior are significantly related or positively correlated. Then the fourth hypothesis is accepted. This is in line with research conducted by van Geel et al. (2017) which shows that psychopathy can predict bullying behavior. When psychopathy is high, the level of bullying behavior will tend to be high. Conversely, when psychopathy is low, the level of bullying behavior will tend to be low. Similar research conducted by Fatima & Sehar (2016) also revealed that psychopathy positively predicts bullying behavior. Another study conducted by Däderman & Ragnestål-Impola (2019) showed that psychopathy is positively correlated with bullying and psychopathy significantly predicts bullying behavior in the workplace.

Psychopathy is a personality dimension centered on dislike and lack of emotion, has no sense of remorse, and is demonstrated by an antagonistic interpersonal style that includes subtle forms of interaction full of contempt, retaliation, and ridicule (Jones & Paulhus, 2010). The characteristics of psychopathic individuals according to Lilienfeld & Widows's (in Habibah, 2023) are that they tend to be charming or attractive to others, impulsive, immune to stress, unfeeling, cold emotions, and unsentimental. Sari & Andriani (2022) explain that psychopathy personality lacks empathy and remorse, is selfish, uncaring, impulsive, and inconsistent. Adrianty et al (2023) reported that dark triad personality, especially psychopathy has the highest influence on bullying behavior.

Dark triad personality is a personality that focuses on three traits, namely machiavellianism, narcissism, and psychopathy with antagonistic, selfish, aggressive, and exploitative traits that refer to ignoring social norms (Banowati & Nugraha, 2022). Rizal & Handayani (2021) explain that machiavellianism refers to the tendency to manipulate others, narcissism is characterized by excessive self-assessment, while psychopathy is characterized as an individual who lacks empathy and a sense of caring for others. Based on the results of the study, dark triad personality is positively associated with bullying behavior. This happens because one of the determining factors for a person in behavior is personality (Rizal & Handayani, 2021). Bullying is a repetitive hurtful behavior that makes the victim feel depressed and is carried out by a strong party against a weaker party (Setiyanawati, 2023). The existence of bullying in schools will certainly have an impact on students who are victims. Kanda & Rosulliya (2024) explained that the impact of bullying can cause prolonged trauma for victims. In addition, victims of bullying also have the potential to experience a decrease in academic grades, be socially shunned, not have close friends, not have a good relationship with parents, decreased mental health, and the worst can lead to depression and trigger suicide. Therefore, schools need to increase supervision and establish bullying prevention measures to reduce bullying behavior in schools.

In addition to the dark triad personality, there are other factors that can influence bullying. Korua et al (2015) in their research revealed that parental parenting is related to bullying behavior in adolescent vocational students. Peer influence is also one of the factors that can increase bullying behavior in students (Aminah & Nurdianah, 2019). Research conducted by Usman (2013) on high school students shows that there is a significant influence between personality, adolescent interpersonal communication with parents, the role of peers, and school climate on bullying behavior in students.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, it is known that there is a relationship between two dimension of dark triad personality and bullying behavior in Vocational High School students. Narcissism has the strongest relationship with bullying behavior in X Vocational High School students with a percentage relationship of 7.3%. Followed by psychopathy which also has a positive relationship with bullying behavior in X Vocational High School students with a percentage relationship of 7.2%. In contrast to most other studies which reveal that machiavellianism has a relationship with bullying behavior, the results of this study found that there is no relationship between machiavellianism and bullying

behavior. This could be influenced by culture, where Indonesia tends to have a culture of collectivism that prioritizes group interests over personal interests.

In order to reduce bullying behavior in schools, it can be done by integrating character education into the school curriculum to teach values such as empathy, respect, and responsibility. In addition, schools can also create a clear and firm anti-bullying policy. This policy includes a definition of bullying, easy reporting procedures, and consequences for bullying perpetrators.

Limitations and Recommendations

The weaknesses and limitations in this study are that when the research took place, there were 12 students who were not present when giving the second questionnaire so that the total subjects decreased from 89 students to 77 students. In addition, researchers only focused on looking at the relationship between the three traits of the dark triad personality with bullying behavior so that they could not reveal other factors that were related to or could influence bullying behavior in adolescents, especially Vocational High School. In addition, there is no provision of treatment to reduce bullying behavior in students.

In order to reduce bullying behavior in schools, it can be done by integrating character education into the school curriculum to teach values such as empathy, respect and responsibility. In addition, schools can also create a clear and firm anti-bullying policy. This policy includes a definition of bullying, easy reporting procedures, and consequences for bullying perpetrators. This study only focuses on looking at the relationship between dark triad personality and bullying behavior, where dark triad personality is an internal factor. So that future researchers are expected to examine other factors, such as external factors of bullying behavior.

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